

Practices and Challenges of Change Management in the Ethiopian Federal Supreme Court

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ABSTRACT: The current study examined the practice and challenges of change management in the Ethiopian Federal Supreme Court. This study adopted a descriptive design with a mixed approach. The objective of the study is to describe the practice, attitudes, and challenges of employees and leaders in the Federal Supreme Court. Primary data was collected by using a questionnaire and interview on the other hand, secondary data was collected from unpublished materials like reports and manuals of the court. 204 respondents who properly completed and returned the questionnaires and five interviewed leaders are involved as sources of data. In order to select respondents, a simple random sampling technique was used. The analysis and summary of findings reflected major practices of change management, perception, and challenges of employees. The organization faces many challenges in the implementation of change management among these, a lack of knowledge about change management, employee resistance, insufficient employee participation in training, and the change management process is the main. The study concludes that the change held in the organization is not satisfactory. It is recommended that for Federal Supreme Court become more successful participate employees in the change management process to reduce challenges and in order to achieve its goal.

KEYWORDS: Change management, Federal Supreme Court, Organizational change.

1. INTRODUCTION

Organizational change is a process by which a large company or organization changes its working methods or aims. Reasons or desires to re-orient might include the need to develop and deal with new situations or markets (Beer, Einstat & Spector, 1990). Organizational change is at the core of an organization's existence because it occurs with increasing frequency and magnitude in both the public and private sectors. Given this reality, the concept of change management has emerged as key for organizations. Change management is defined as the coordination of a structured period of transition from situation A to situation B in order to achieve lasting change within an organization (Bartkus, 1997). Change Management is a systematic activity to prepare an organization for and implement ongoing environmental changes in a business operation. So, change management is about innovative strategies and speedy activities to deal with variable and sudden changes. (Hegde, 2000).

According to Moran and Brightman (2001), change management is the process of continually renewing an organization's direction, structure, and capabilities to serve the ever-changing needs of external and internal customers. A study by Simon (2012) confirmed that some of the important factors that influence the outcome of process improvement programs in organizations include strategic alignment, structural alignment, IT alignment, executive commitment, and employee empowerment. Other factors he found to be significant and critical to the success of process improvement programs were the value and clarity of the proposed changes, the pace of the change, the inherent culture of an organization, the sustainability of the change, and skills. To remain competitive and prosper in today's dynamic business environment, managers in organizations must continually be innovative and adaptive to new change management practices and techniques in line with the changing world.

Changes can occur at different levels: individual level, group level, or organizational structure level. However, a change in the organizational structure influences individuals and groups changes more than changes in the individual and group level affect the organization (Francesco & Gold, 1998). Managers and employees may view change differently and the level of interest in change

varies from person to person and from hierarchical level to hierarchical level. What top managers see as an opportunity to strengthen the business is viewed by many employees as disruptive and unnecessary and vice versa (Francesco & Gold, 1998).

Ackerman (1997) has distinguished between three types of change. According to Ackerman the first type of change is developmental change. It may be either planned or emergent; it is first order, or incremental. It is changing management that enhances or corrects existing aspects of an organization, often focusing on the improvement of a skill or process. The second type of change is a transitional change which seeks to achieve a known desired state that is different from the existing one. It is episodic, planned and second order, or radical. Much of the organizational change literature is based on this type. The last change type is called transformational change which is radical or second-order in nature. It requires a shift in assumptions made by the organization and its members. Transformation can result in an organization that differs significantly in terms of structure, processes, culture, and strategy. It may, therefore, result in the creation of an organization that operates in a developmental mode – one that continuously learns, adapts, and improves, Ackerman (1997).

According to Lorenzi and Riley (2000), change is a good opportunity for employees to take stock of where they stand. Routine performance in a job might have led the employee into a state of a rut, with the employee unaware of the stagnation he or she experiences. Change, by demolishing the existing set up forces employees to review where they stand, and take corrective steps to get back on track if required. Such a review also provides the employee with a good opportunity to make a career change. Change usually comes with career coaching, workshops, and career counseling, all tools that help employees take stock of their careers. The biggest benefits of organizational change on employees are the training and development opportunities that usually accompany change. Companies that embark on change invariably provide training and development programs to help employees cope with the new requirements. This becomes a valuable opportunity for employees to update their skill sets, and acquire new and industry-relevant skills. Employees who miss such opportunities run the risk of stagnation, for the skills they acquired in college and at work might have become obsolete, requiring a change in the first place (Lorenzi and Riley, 2000).

Change is important in organizations to allow employees to learn new skills, explore new opportunities, and exercise their creativity in ways that ultimately benefit the organization through new ideas and increased commitment. Preparing employees to deal with these changes involves an analysis of the tools and training required to help them learn new skills. Training can be provided through traditional classroom settings or, increasingly, through online learning opportunities. Importantly, organizations need to do a good job of evaluating employees' capabilities and then taking steps to fill the gaps between current skills and the skills required to respond to growth, (Lin Gensing-pophal; 2010).

Recent statistics reveal that only one-third of organizational change efforts were considered successful by their leaders. Apparently, implementing successful change programs in organizations is quite problematic. The low success rates of change programs are often attributed to resistance to change on the part of employees. However, a more nuanced view of resistance to change and its determinants might be more appropriate (Jos & Hotman, 2012).

Ethiopian public service organizations have been under change for the last two decades during which many reform programs and change tools have been implemented. Welansa Wegayehu, (2009) has conducted an assessment of change management in one of these sectors the Ethiopian Revenue and Customs Authority, and concluded that the leadership in ERCA assumes the role of a change agent and has the commitment to getting the revenue sector transformed, but most of the managers in middle and lower levels, as well as the employees, lack determination, courage, and skills of management in the level that radical change requires. Additionally, she recommended the leadership needs to create a conducive environment by embracing more change agents in the reengineering effort. The aim of the current study was to access the practices and challenges of change management in the Ethiopian federal supreme court (EFSC).

2. RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODS

2.1. Research Type & Approach

This study would apply the descriptive research type because descriptive research is concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual, a group, or of an event as it exists at present (Kothari, 1990). This study used a mixed approach that is both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The mixed approach helps to make an investigation on change management to gain a better understanding by obtaining data from different sources, such as interviews and questionnaires. Accordingly, concurrent mixed

method design has been applied in order to gain a better understanding and possibly for a more insightful interpretation of the results to examine the challenges of change management in the case of the federal supreme court.

2.2. Data Types and Sources

Both primary and secondary sources of data was used in order to collect appropriate data. Primary data has been collected from top-level managers, directorates, and workers through questionnaires and interviews. The secondary data has been collected from different unpublished materials like reports and manuals of the court, policy documents, and other relevant materials would be reviewed.

2.3. Data Collection Techniques/Instruments

In order to obtain relevant and adequate information questionnaire and an interview was used as instruments for data collection. The questionnaire consists of both open and closed-ended questions designed and distributed to the employees to collect data about change management. Semi-structured interviews have been conducted with the directorate of the strategic management office and the directorate of the human resource office so as to enhance the internal validity of the instrument. Because this method involves direct interaction between the researcher and a respondent and hence, it gives chance to move the conversation in any direction of interest that may come and is also used to ask questions that were not included in the structured interview in case new questions are raised as ideas emerge through the process. Because using only one type of interview (structured or Unstructured) might lead to less rich data or information. Generally, the interview has been held with top-level managers or directorates of the Court at different levels believing that they have deep and relevant information about the issues and it would be conducted face to face with the help of different ways like from the basis of their idea prepares related questions in order to minimize information loss.

2.4. Population of the Study

This study was conducted at the federal Supreme Court. The population of this study comprised all the members of FSC. Presently FSC has got nineteen Work Processes namely; President's Office; Vice President's Office; Judge Administration Council; Registrar Office; Court manager Office; Women and Youth Affairs Directorate; Audit Directorate; General Service; Finance Directorate; Human Resource Management Directorate; Strategic planning and Management Directorate; Public Relation and Communication Directorate; Purchasing and procurement management Directorate; Legal Study and Supportive Team; ICT Directorate; Inspection and Judicial Investigation Directorate; Training Directorate; Federal Attorney General; Federal Courts Judgment Execution Directorate. In all nineteen, Directorates there is a total of 498 employees.

2.5. Sample and Sampling Techniques

Simple random sampling (SRS) was used to select the respondents. This design allows the population to have an equal chance of being selected in the sample. The sample size has been 221 respondents out of a target population of 493. These were selected to ensure that the sampling size had the characteristic representation of the population using the formulae developed by Solvins (2012).

2.6. Data Analysis Method

Once the data was collected using qualitative and quantitative approaches then it would be analyzed through the descriptive method. The quantitative data were analyzed through percentages and cross-tabulations. Accordingly, some data analysis methods such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standardization have been employed for the purpose of data analysis and interpretation (Best and Kahn, 2003:373). The qualitative data also were analyzed through the descriptive narrative method.

3. RESULT

3.1 Response Rate

The primary data was collected using questionnaires and face-to-face interviews. Out of 221 questionnaires distributed to EFSC employees, 204 were collected. The response rate is 92.3% and face-to-face interviews with 5 directorate directors and team leaders were held successfully. As a result, the response rate for interview data collection was 100%.

3.2 Demography Characteristic of Respondents

In this study, respondents' profiles were described in terms of Gender, Age group, educational background, and Work experience. The study used four parts of questionnaires. The first part is a demographic part, the second is the practice of change management,

the third part the t is the perception of employees towards change management, and the fourth part is the challenge of change management in the court.

Out of the total respondents, most (57%) respondents were male that is and the rest 43% respondents are females. In terms of age 26% of respondents were between 25 – 30, 23.5% of respondents were between 36 – 40, 22% of respondents are between 31 -36, 17% of the respondents were under the age of 25 and the rest 11% respondents are above 40 years old. This shows that most of the respondents were between 25-30 years old. This implies that most Ethiopian federal supreme court (EFSC) employees are young and inspirational.

Based on the study the education level of the respondents indicated that the majority of the respondents (n=106, 52%) was degree holder, (n=63, 31%) of respondents had a Diploma, (n=21,10%) of the respondents were certificate level, n=12, 6% of the respondents were above twelve grade and the rest (n=2, 1%) employees were high school completed. From this data, we could conclude that the majority of employees were first-degree/bachelor graduates.

On the other hand, the work experience of the respondents indicated that (n=16, 8%) of the respondents have less than one year of work experience, (n=70, 34%) of respondents have 1-3 years of work experience in the organization and the comparable level (n=67, 33%) of respondents have more than 10 years of experience, (n=39, 19%) respondents have 4-6 years of work experience, and (n=12, 6%) respondents have 7-9 years of experience. This demonstrates that the court staff is equipped with beginners and a lot of work experience. Among these respondents, 189 (95%) of them were non-Managerial in position and the rest 15 (7%) of respondents were Managerial.

3.3. Descriptive Analysis of Basic Research Questions

3.3.1. Practice of Change Management

The assessment of employee awareness on how to practice change management indicated 52% of them have awareness of how to practice and the rest 48% of respondents had not been aware. This fact indicated that half of EFSC employees know about the practice of change management in the organization. But half of the employees did not know how.

The information gathered through interviews carried out with the management and directorates said change management is implemented in the court. But the process is slow. Occasional training is given in the court, but not enough. The office has to work a lot. On the other hand, the study on the importance of change in an organization indicated that the majority of employees 169(83%) of respondents agreed change management is important for the organization but 35(17%) opposed it.

As per summarized open-ended questionnaires, respondents explained that change management helped to implement the plan successfully. It helped the organization to achieve its vision and mission effectively. It initiates employees to serve his /her work with integrity, accountability, and transparency. It improved the organization's achievement. It could increase customer satisfaction. It could help to generate new ideas and arrangements. It could help to point out challenges and take action and be a competitor in the market. On the other hand, interviewed responded, change management tools help to implement tasks efficiently and effectively. And also, the client will be compensated properly. However, the changing tools currently underway in our country are not that much well-matched with the judicial system. Therefore, their value is low to the organization and they are not much effective in the court.

3.3.2. Participation of Respondents in the change management process in the Organization

The study on the participation of employees in the change management process indicated (n=118, 58%) of respondents said that they did not participate in the change management process in the organization. Whereas, the remains 86(42%) respondents got a chance to participate in the change management process. As participated respondents expressed that they participated in different training related to change management and all participated as change management team leaders and members. All interview respondents have had the opportunity to participate in the organization's change process.

3.3.3. The Reason to drive change management

The assessment of the reason to drive change management indicated 38(17%) of respondents agreed employees need derived change effort in the organization, 72(35%) of respondents agreed on customer needs derived change effort in the organization, 8(4%) of respondents agreed on change in industry or market condition derived change effort in the organization, 39(19%) of respondents agreed on competitive advantage of new opportunities derived change effort in the organization, 51(25%) of respondents agreed to shift government policy derived change effort in the organization and nobody responded others reasons drive change effort in the organization. As the result, it is possible to understand that customer needs and shifting government policy are the main sources to

drive change efforts in the EFSC. In the interview, almost all the interview respondents explained that drive change agent in the court were mostly customers next to them in government policy.

3.3.4. Initiate of the change effort

Based on the study the initiation of the change effort indicated 68% (138) respondents said change initiator were customer, 20 (42) % change initiator were manager and 12%(24) of respondents said change initiator were employee in the organization. The study showed that customers were change initiator in federal Supreme Court. Here, the study deduced change effort in the organization was initiated by customers.

3.3.5. Response of worker to change effort initiated by management

Out of the 204 respondents in the current study response of workers to change efforts initiated by management showed that more than half 113 (55%) of respondents said managers had a moderate commitment to initiate change efforts. 38(19%) of respondents agree the management has a high commitment to initiate change effort, 34(17%) of respondents considered the management has a very high commitment to initiate change effort, 10(5%) of respondents consider a very low commitment to initiate change effort and the remaining 9(4%) of respondents agree with that the management has a low commitment to initiate change efforts. As a result, most workers believed that managers had a moderate commitment to initiate change management efforts in the EFSC.

3.3.6. Consideration of managers about change management initiatives

Of the total, 204 respondents in study 144(56%) of respondents agreed managers considered change initiatives brought by employees. But 90(44%) respondents did not agree with this idea. In open-ended questions, some employees explained there was not enough participation of employees in the change initiative process. Leaders didn't consider subordinates' thoughts. Leaders didn't ask and accept employees' ideas. There was no readiness to quit the previous habit. On the other hand, Interviewees said reasons for change by employees are also a source of change. Although changes are often made by government-driven guidelines, staff opinions are taken into account a little.

3.3.7. Respondents' response about Change agents

The result of the Respondents' responses about Change agents showed that 122 (60%) of the respondents agreed there were change agents in the organization, and 66(32%) of the respondents agreed there were no change agents in the organization. However, 16(8%) of respondents were neutral to answer the question. From this data, we observed that there were change agents in the court.

3.3.8. Respondent's outlook on change agent to build effective change

The result of the organization change agent's effort in effectively introducing change looks, 54(39%) of respondents said that the activity of the change agents effort was medium in effectively introducing change in EFSC, 27(20%) said that the activity of change agents effort was worst in effectively introducing change in FSC, 17(12%) said that the activity of change agents effort was very low in effectively introducing change in FSC, 11(8%) said that the activity of change agents effort was low in effectively introducing change in EFSC, 14(10 %) said that the activity of change agents effort was excellent in effectively introducing change in FSC and the remaining 15(11%) reported that the activity of change agents effort was very good in effectively introducing change in EFSC. So from this fact we could conclude change agents did not introduce change effectively as expected.

3.3.9. Respondents outlook about outcome of change

The result of the positive outcome of change management indicated almost half of respondents that means 94(46%) agreed that the change effort brought positive outcome and 74(36%) of respondents answered it was difficult to measure. 28(14%) of the respondent agreed the change didn't bring positive outcomes and only 8(4%) of respondents didn't know the change efforts outcome. From the result it inferred that change efforts brought positive outcome in the court.

3.4. Perception of Employees towards Change Management

3.4.1. The respondent's outlook regarding change management

Table 1. change management practice look like

	Respondents		
	Item	Frequency	Percent
Change management practice in the organization looks like	Highly satisfactory	12	6%
	Satisfactory	32	15.5%
	Medium	106	52%
	dissatisfactory	18	9%

	Highly dissatisfactory	36	17.5%
	Total	204	100%

Source: Compiled from own survey, 2018

As presented in Table 1, how the organization’s change management looks like, above half 106(52%) respondents replied that change management practice was medium. 32(15.5%) and 12% of respondents answered the court change management practice was satisfactory and highly dis satisfactory respectively. 18(9%) and 36(17%) respondents believe that there were dissatisfactory and highly dissatisfactory change management practices. From this result, we could recognize that the effectiveness of change management in the court is fair/medium.

3.4.2. Respondents’ awareness about change management tools

Table 2. Awareness of change management tools

	Respondents		
	Item	Frequency	Percent
Management tools well- known to you	BSC	140	68%
	BPR	110	54%
	MBO	30	15%
	Citizen charter	40	20%
	Total		

Source: compiled from own survey, 2018

As shown in Table 2, Out of 204 respondents, 140(68%) of them said that they knew well BSC tool, 110 (54% %) of them said that BPR was well known for them. The rest 40 (20%) and (15%) of them said that they knew well citizen charter tool and MBO tool respectively. The interview respondents also accepted the idea that BSC relatively the most used tool in the court. Thus, the fact the majority of respondents said researcher could recognize that BSC was well known by employees than others tool.

3.4.3. The effectiveness change management tool in the organization

Table 3. Effective change management tools

	Respondents		
	Item	Frequency	Percent
Which change management tool were effective for your organization	BSC	136	67%
	BPR	128	63%
	MBO	18	9%
	Citizen charter	30	15%
	Total		

Source: compiled from own survey, 2018

As indicated in table 3, out of 204 respondents 136(67%) of them said that a balanced score card (BSC) was an effective change management tool for the organization,128 (63 %) said that BPR was effective and the rest 15% and 9% reported that citizen charter and Management by objective (MBO) can be effective for the organization respectively. Interviewees said among the tools BSC is the most effective tools for the court. From employees thought we could understand that BSC and Business Process Reengineering (BPR) were effective tools for their organization than others tool in the court. According to the interviewee, despite the effort to carry out a variety of changing devices in the court, only BSC was possible to deliver to employees.

3.4.4 Response of Perception of employees towards change and change management

Table 4. the perception of employees toward changes

	Statements		Strongly agree	Agree	undecided	disagree	Strongly disagree
I	It can improve our status	N	65	113	12	14	0
		%	32	55	6	7	0
II	Change is important to our organization	N	81	99	10	10	4
		%	39	49	5	5	2
III	Employees have readiness in terms of mentality, skill competence toward change	N	78	89	22	12	3
		%	38	44	11	6	1
IV	Employees have been committed to change	N	64	86	26	28	0
		%	31	42	13	14	0
V	Employee perception is positive toward target achievement/outcome	N	51	102	36	12	3
		%	25	50	18	6	1

Source: compiled from own survey, 2018

Table 4, item no –I, 113(55%) respondents agreed and 65(32 %) strongly agreed that change improved employee’s status at FSC. while 12(6%) respondents had undecided and the rest 14(7%) of the respondents were disagreed. Thus, it could be inferred that the majority of respondents recognized that change improves the status of employees.

Table 4, item no –II, shows 81(39 %) and 99(49 %) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed” change is important for the organization” respectively but 10(5%) of respondents said neutral, 10(5%) of them disagreed and 4(2%) of respondent were strongly disagreed. As a result of this fact, the majority of respondents identify were agreed change was important for FSC.

Table 4, understatement (III) majority of respondents which means 38% and 44% strongly agreed and agreed that employees are ready to change in terms of mentality, skill, and, competency respectively. But 11% had undecided, 6% disagreed and 1% strongly disagreed with the statement. Thus, the researcher understood that almost (82%) of the respondents were agreed that employees ready for change management in FSC. Understatement (VI) 31% and 42% of respondents strongly agreed and agreed that "employees have been committed toward change in EFSC". While 13% of them were impartial and 14% disagreed with the statement employee have been committed to change. As a result, from this data, we can conclude that employees were committed to change (Table 4).

As presented in Table 4, statement(v), out of the total respondent, 51(25%) of the respondents were strongly agree that “Employee perception was positive toward target achievement/outcome”, 102(50%) of respondents agreed “Employee perception was positive toward target achievement/outcome”, 36(18%) of respondents have undecided regarding the statement that “employee perception was positive toward target achievement/outcome”, 12(6%) of respondents disagreed “Employee perception was positive toward target achievement/outcome” and 3(1%) were strongly disagree with the statement. The researcher concludes that the above employee’s perception was positive toward target achievement. In general, the perceptions of employees toward change management are positive. Changes brought improvement status, employees were ready in all aspects, committed, and positive to do in all capacities and perform target achievement.

3.4.5. Different Benefits of implementing change management

Table 5. Benefits of implementing change management

No	Statement		Strongly agree	agree	undecided	disagree	Strongly disagree
1	Improve personal performance	N	54	98	24	22	6
		%	26	48	12	11	3
2	Improve employee satisfaction	N	48	92	34	28	2
		%	23.5	45	16.5	14	1

3	Improve achievement of the strategic goal of the organization	N	43	115	28	13	5
		%	21	56	14	6	3
4	Increase of customer satisfaction	N	59	98	31	14	2
		%	29	48	15	7	1

Source: compiled from own survey, 2018

As indicated in table 5, under (statement 1) 98(48 %) of respondents agreed that implementing change management "Improves personal performance", and 54(26%) strongly agreed that implementing change management "improves personal performance". 24(12%) of respondents undecided and the remaining 22(11%) and 6(3%) disagreed and strongly disagreed with statement.

Table 5, understatement (2), 48(23.5%) of respondents strongly agreed that implementing change management Improved employee satisfaction, and 92(45%) agreed that implementing change management Improved employee satisfaction by change management which held in the organization improved employee satisfaction. 34(6.5%) undecided and the remains 28(14 %) and 2(1%) disagree and strongly disagreed with the statement respectively.

As indicated in Table 5, understatement (3),43(21%) of respondents agreed that implementation change management improved the achievement of the strategic goal of the organization, and 115(56 %) strongly agreed that implementation change management improved the achievement of Strategic Goal of the organization. 22% of respondent's undecided about the idea. 6% and 3% disagreed and strongly disagreed that the implementation changes in management improved the achievement of the strategic goal of the organization,

Table 5, understatement (4) out of the total respondents, 59(29%) and 98(48%) respondents agreed and strongly agreed that implementation of change management practice could increase customer satisfaction respectively, 31(15%) respondents were undecided with the statement. The remains 14(7%) disagreed and 2(1%) strongly disagreed by the idea. As a result of this data, we can conclude that the organization's change management practice increases customer satisfaction.

3.5. Challenges of change management

3.5.1. Response of main challenge and barriers the organization faced during major change

Table 6. Rate the main challenges and barriers that the organizations face during Major changes

No	Statement		Strongly agree	agree	undecided	disagree	Strongly disagree
I	Lack of knowledge about change management	N	64	93	26	17	2
		%	31	46	13	8	1
II	Employee resistance	N	72	43	25	53	12
		%	35	21	12	26	6
III	Managers resistance	N	45	61	28	56	14
		%	22	30	14	27	7
VI	Insufficient employee participation in training	N	62	73	30	29	11
		%	30	36	15	14	5
V	Insufficient employee participation on change management process	N	62	94	23	15	10
		%	30	46	11	8	5
VI	Employees treats the work atmosphere	N	39	73	27	43	22
		%	19	36	13	21	11

Source: Compiled from own survey, 2018

As indicated understatement (I) in table 15,64 (31 %) of respondents strongly agreed that challenge of change management was lack of knowledge and 93(46%) agreed that challenge of change management was lack of knowledge. 26(13%) of respondent’s undecided and the re strongly main 17(8%) and 2(1%) disagreed and strongly disagreed that the challenge of change management was lack of knowledge. Thus, the researcher conclude that the majority of respondents agreed one of the challenges of change management was a lack of knowledge.

As seen in table 6, understatement (II), 43(21%) and 72(35%) respondents strongly agreed and agreed that challenge of change management was employees’ resistance respectively, and 25(12%) of respondents remained undecided. 53(26%) and 12(6%) of respondents strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively that challenge of change management was employees resistance. as a result of the premises of the research majority of respondents agreed one of the challenges of change management was employee’s resistance

As indicated table 6, under statement (III) more than half of respondents that mean 45(22%) of respondents agreed that challenge of change management was management resistance respectively and 62(30 %) strongly agreed that challenge of change management was management resistance respectively. 14% of respondent’s undecided through the idea. 27% and 7% disagreed and strongly disagreed that challenge of change management was management resistance respectively.

As result from the data found one of the challenges of change management was management resistance. Similarly, as shown Table 6, under statement (IV), majority of respondents that means62 (30%) and 73(36%) of respondents agreed and strongly agreed insufficient employee participation in training was the main challenge during the organization change management practice. 30(15%) of respondent’s undecided with statement. The rest 29(14%) & 11(5 %) disagreed and strongly disagreed by the idea. As result from the data found one of the challenges of change management was insufficient employee participation in training. As indicated as shown Table 6, under statement (V), 64(30 %) and 94(46 %) of respondents strongly agreed and agreed insufficient employee participation on change management process is the main challenge in the organization. 23(11%) of respondent’s undecided through the idea. 15(8%) and 10(5%) disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement. As result from the data found most of one of the challenges of change management was insufficient employee participation on change management process. As it can be seen table 6, under statement (VI), 39(19 %) and 73(36 %) of respondents strongly agreed and agreed that challenge of change management was Employees were treated the work atmosphere respectively. 11% of respondent’s undecided through the idea. 21% and 11% disagreed and strongly disagreed challenge of change management was Employees treated the work atmosphere respectively. As result from the premises of the research employees treated the work atmosphere was not challenges of change management. According to interviewees, the staff resisted change because they were afraid of losing their jobs. Leaders are also scared to embrace new ideas. To address this problem, efforts have been made to participate the leaders in various training and to try to convince them by participate in various discussions. But there is no enough involvement for employees.

3.5.2. Different reasons for resistance

Table 7. reasons for employee’s resistance

No	Statement		Strongly agree	agree	Medium	disagree	Strongly disagree
1	Employees’ resistance is one of the major challenges due to fear job displacement and lack of incentives packages:	N	33	52	37	62	20
		%	17	25	18	30	10

Source: Compiled from own survey, 2018

As indicated in the Table 7, 33(17%) and 52(25%) of respondents strongly agreed and agreed by employees resist due to fear of job displacement and lack of incentive package, 18% employees have medium suggestion. And 30% and 10% respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed by the statement respectively. From this result we can recognize that employee resistance due to fear job displacement and lack of incentives packages was average.

3.5.3. Response on leadership resistance during change management

Table 8. Reason of resistance

No	Statement	N	Strongly agree	Agree	Medium	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	Change management in the organization is challenged due to lack of committed and visionary leadership:	N	52	41	48	43	19
		%	26	20	24	21	9
2	Inadequate understanding about change management to give supports to performers is another challenge to managers	N	56	73	40	24	11
		%	27	36	20	12	5

Source: Compiled from own survey, 2018

As illustrated in the above table (table 8) Item 1, 52(26%) and 41(20%) of respondents strongly agreed and agreed with the report of lack of committed and visionary leadership is the main challenge in the court. 48(24%) had medium thought but 43(21%) and 19 (9%) respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed by the statement. From this data we can conclude lack of committed and visionary leadership was one reason for change resistance. In the Item 2, 56(27%) and 73 (36%) respondents strongly agreed that Inadequate understanding managers couldn't support performers, agreed Inadequate understanding managers couldn't support performers. 40(20 %) had medium thought but 24 (12%) and 11(5%) respondents disagree and strongly disagree by the statement. From this data we can conclude that inadequate understanding of managers about change management the main challenge.

3.5.4. Response Top management

Table 9. Top Management

No	Statement	NO	Strongly agree	agree	Medium	disagree	Strongly disagree
1	Top managers' fear to support the new values and beliefs required by the redesigned processes of change management because of technical and political reasons:	N	41	86	37	32	8
		%	20	42	18	16	4
2	Lack of total involvements of top management who have real power to bring change and become change agent is another challenges faced.	N	48	71	40	39	6
		%	23	35	20	19	3

Source: Compiled from own survey, 2018

Table 9, 41(20%) of respondents strongly agreed that Top managers' feared to support the new values and beliefs required by the redesigned Processes of change management because of technical and political reasons:86(42%) of respondents agreed that Top managers' feared to support the new values and beliefs required by the redesigned Processes of change management because of technical and political reasons,37(18%)of respondents medium but32(16%) of respondents disagreed that Top managers' feared to support the new values and beliefs required by the redesigned Processes of change management because of technical and political reasons and 8(4%) of respondents strongly disagreed that top managers' feared to support the new values and beliefs required by the redesigned Processes of change management because of technical and political reasons.

In general, the researcher understand one of the challenge of change management were top management unwillingly because of technical and political fear to support the redesign process.

Table 9 shown, statement (2), out of total respondents, 48(23%) of respondents strongly agreed that lack of involvement of top management to bring change were another challenges of change management,71(35%) of respondents agreed that lack of involvement of top management to bring change were another challenges of change management,40 (20%) were medium but 39(19%) of respondents disagreed that lack of involvement of top management to bring change were another challenges of change

management and 6 (3%) of respondents disagreed that top management did lack of involvement to bring change were another challenges of change management. From this data researcher could conclude that lack of involvement of top management to bring change were another challenges of change management.

In interview the respondents said most the time the team leaders and expert gave trainee trainer to experts and professionals in EFSC. they also provide training to managements and employees. Management actively took training and participates in the change process. The changes actually brought some changes but not much effective .among change management tool relatively BSC brought some changes in court. On the other hand, BPR was challenge to be effective in court.

The interviewee gave some suggestion about change management the main source of change management government policy this might be a problem to practice it .it may be effective, successful and help other organizations. In the meantime, the nature and culture of the organization may affect the changes or incompatible to do with changes. Change management practice should be based on the organization nature and culture. Unless, the change became fruitless practice in the organization.

4. DISCUSSIONS

The purpose of the study was to assess the overall organizational change management practice, perception of employees, and challenges in the case of the Ethiopian Federal Supreme Court. The study has taken on a descriptive case study of research design by using both qualitative and quantitative methods, Semi-structured interviews. This design was assumed to be appropriate because it helps in disclosing some of the major practices, challenges, best results, and employees' perceptions on the basis of data gathered at a point in time (Bryman & Bell, 2007).

Data gathering tools were questionnaires and interviews. Regarding the respondent for the study, 221 respondents were included in the study using simple random sampling. 204 were returned and include in the study and the major findings were summarized under each research question.

The gender distribution in the Ethiopian Federal Supreme Court (EFSC) was almost fair in the proportion which means 57% male and 43% female. Slightly higher than half of the employees (52%) were college graduates and (72%) of the employees were between 25-40 years old. Thus, they are productive and inspirational. There are well-experienced and binger employees in EFSC. More than half (52%) of EFSC employees did know how to practice change management in the organization. Mainly change management practice helps to achieve the objective of EFSC. Customer needs and shifting government policy main sources to drive change efforts in the EFSC. Customers mainly initiated change in the EFSC. Change agents did not introduce change effectively as expected. Change efforts brought positive outcomes in the court. The practice of change management is improved. The balanced scorecard (BSC) was a more effective tool for their organization than other tools in the court. Change management improves the status of employees and is important to the EFSC.

On the Other hand, based on the study the perception of employees toward change has been evaluated and the practice of change management in the court is medium. BSC was well known by employees and more effective than other tools in the court. Most employees' perceptions indicated employees are ready mentally, have skill competency, and are committed in all aspects to change management and positive toward target achievement in EFSC. Most employee respondents agree implementation of change management improved personal performance, employee satisfaction achievement of the strategic goal of the organization, and increased customer satisfaction.

The critical challenges of change management agreed by employee respondents were lack of knowledge, employee resistance, and managers' resistance to insufficient employee participation in training, employees' treat the work atmosphere and insufficient employee participation in the change management process. Employees resist due to fear of job displacement and lack of incentive packages. According to the employees' suggestion, a lack of committed and visionary leadership was one cause for change resistance. The majority of employees showed challenges of change management were inadequate understanding of managers about change management, top management unwillingly because of technical and political fear to support the redesign process of change management, and lack of involvement of top management.

5. CONCLUSION

Organizational Change Management (OCM) is a framework for managing the effect of new business processes, new technology, shifting economic landscapes, or changes in organizational structure and culture within an enterprise. The aim of this study was to

assess the overall organizational change management practice and challenges in the Ethiopian Federal Supreme Court. Specifically, describing practices of change management in the organization examines leaders' and employees' attitudes towards change management, and identifies challenges that are faced during the change management process. Demographic characteristic expressed in the study was men and women employees of the EFSC, who were young, educated well experienced, energetic, and resourceful to do their job effectively. EFSC exercised different practices of change management and accepted its importance. Those practices relatively effectively used balanced scorecards (BSC) and Business Process Reengineering (BPR) to do better and improve organizational operations in general, and change management practice helps to achieve their objective of Ethiopian federal supreme courts (EFSC) in particular. The main source to drive change management efforts were customer needs and shifting government policy. Change agents did not introduce change effectively as expected. However, change management efforts brought positive outcomes in the Federal Supreme Court. As per the discussion in the research, most employees perceived employees ready physically and mentally with skill competency and committed to change management toward target achievement in EFSC. As explained in the discussion by most respondents and interviewees serious challenge of change management is related to lack of knowledge, employee resistance, manager resistance, insufficient employee participation in training, employee treats the work atmosphere and insufficient employee participation in the change management process. Besides, inadequate understanding of managers about change management, top management reluctance to support the change process, and lack of involvement also challenge the effectiveness of change management in the EFSC. Due to the limited participation of employees in the process of change management and fear of job displacement employees resist the change. The organization implements the change by using the change team and top management. The majority of respondents indicated that the change held in EFSC is not enough. EFSC has enough staff to do change management effectively. According to the data gathered, the company has sufficient employees to accomplish change management practices properly. This would help them to do efficiently and effectively their activity. Therefore, it is advisable for the organization to provide continuous training for workers to increase their workforce and motivate them. The court should not only change its policy when changing government policy; however, it is better to make the court proceed with the creation of a justifiable change in the court system. Leaders do not create political and technical reasons for changes, but it's better to be resourceful by removing challenges. Better communication to reduce the communication gap between management and employee to deal with the necessary idea in the change management practice. It should be two-way communication to fill and accommodate the gap between employees and management. It is suggested that the court provide better training to the change management team and leaders to have enough knowledge about change management. And also it is recommended that the change team be introduced to the staff about change as expected. It is advisable for the court to participate employees adequately in the training and process of change management. It makes the court function better and effectively and enables the court to accomplish its mission.

Giving more emphasis to the challenge of change management EFSC looks for the best mechanism to solve the current challenges. Thus, EFSC should provide adequate training and education to supply the knowledge and avoid employee resistance and manager's resistance, sufficient employee participation has a significant role in the atmosphere of the organization so from the very beginning before and after implementation of change management and its progress the involvement of employee bring the good relationship between employees and management.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declared that there is no conflict of interest with any party in this research work.

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